

PREPARATIONS AND EVALUATION OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY FOR TiB₂/ Al COMPOSITES BY SPARK SINTERING PROCESS

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1 Introduction

Recently, aluminum (Al) matrix composites have been required as the functional materials or materials with good functional and mechanical properties at room and high temperature. Especially, the high-performance heat sink has been used for electronic devices such as Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) and Light Emitting Diode (LED). On the other hand, application to high electrical conducting material such as electrical wire and high voltage line has been expecting, gradually. These composites are required to have good electrical conductivity, good thermal conductivity, low thermal expansion and good mechanical properties at room and high temperatures until 300°C. Previously, SiC particles or fibers dispersed Al (SiC/Al) composites has been studied for thermal and electrical conducting materials. SiC/Al composites are used for recent heat sink in electronic devices. On the other hand, this composite was not used for electrical conducting materials because of low cost performance and low electrical conductivity of SiC. Particularly, the use of carbon fiber (Cf) reinforced Al composites have been increasing because of its excellent thermal and electrical conductivities, low thermal expansion and good mechanical properties. However, the Cf having high electric conductivity is expensive and its composites have high anisotropy, because Cf is long fiber. Therefore, this composite has anisotropic properties. On the other hand, the particle dispersion type composite is high cost performance and its properties are isotropic. Because particles are usually high cost performance compared with long fiber. In this study, we will develop the high electrical conducting materials with isotropic

properties with high cost performance. Table 1 shows the candidate dispersant for Al matrix. Boride ceramics have high thermal and electrical conductivity. In addition, it is expected that heat transfer and electrical conductivity at interface between boride particle and Al is excellent, because boride ceramics are good electrical conductor. Especially, Titanium diboride (TiB₂) has low thermal expansion ($3.7 \times 10^{-6}/K$), high electrical conductivity ($1110 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1}m^{-1}$) and thermal conductivity (100W/mK), and has superior plastic deformation resistance at the high temperature. In addition, TiB₂ does not react with Al [1]. It is expected that TiB₂ powder dispersed Al composite (TiB₂/Al) composites have good thermal and electrical conductivity with low thermal expansion [2, 3]. On the other hand, as spark sintering process has quick densification because of the effective temperature rising, it is suitable sintering process for the preparation of Al matrix composites.

Table 1 Properties of electronic materials

	Density [g/cm ³]	CTE [10 ⁻⁶ /K]	Melting point [°C]	Electron conductivity [10 ⁶ · Ω ⁻¹ · m ⁻¹]
Al	2.7	23.1	660	40.0
SiC	3.22	4.0	2730	0.001
TiB ₂	4.5	3.7	2790	11.1
ZrB ₂	6.11	5.9	3200	10.3

The aim of this study is to obtain the TiB₂/Al composite with superior electric conductivity by spark sintering process. And, as the dispersibility of

particles affect to the functional and mechanical properties, the effect of dispersibility of TiB₂ particles to electrical conductivity was estimated.

2 Experimental Procedure

The pure Al and TiB₂ particle powders used for starting materials are 3μm in average particle size with 99.96% of purity and 2.62 μm in average particle size, respectively. Fig.1 shows the microstructure of as-received Al and TiB₂ powders. Al powders forms spherical. On the other hand, fine TiB₂ aggregate and then, forms big sized secondary particles with 2.62 μm in average size.

Fig. 1 SEM image as-received (a) Al and (b) TiB₂ powders.

A volume ratio of TiB₂ particle and Al powder were set as 1:4, and the mixed powder was obtained by the ball milling method under the conditions of 50rpm for 18h. In this milling process, two ways of

the dry blending in atmosphere and the wet blending in ethanol was carried out. Then, TiB₂/Al composites were fabricated by electric discharge plasma sintering (SPS) method. Fig. 2 shows the spark sintering conditions used in this study.

Fig. 2 Flow chart of spark sintering process.

The sintering conditions were 50MPa in applied pressure, 2.7×10^{-1} Pa in vacuum degree, 4V in voltage, 380~410A in current, 823K in sintering temperature and 1.8ks in keeping time of applied pressure. Density and microstructure of the composites was evaluated by Archimedes method and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). In addition, the dispersibility of the TiB₂ particle in composites was estimated by two-dimensional local number (LN2D) [4]. And, the electrical conductivity of the composite was estimated by four-terminal method.

3 Results and Discussion

Properties of composites were affected by the shape, the size, the volume fraction and the dispersibility of dispersant. In this study, the effect of the dispersibility of TiB₂ particles on the electrical conductivity was investigated.

Fig. 3 shows microstructure of blended powder containing 20vol% TiB₂ and 80vol% Al. Powders were mixed in dry and wet processes. In wet blending, aggregation of TiB₂ particles was not observed. Both particles of Al and TiB₂ were distributed uniformly without aggregation. On the other hand, the aggregation of TiB₂ particles was remained in dry process. Red circle in fig.3 show the aggregation of TiB₂ particles. Average aggregation size of TiB₂ particles seems to be small slightly by dry process.

Fig. 3 SEM image of mixed powder of TiB_2 and Al by (a) wet blending and (b) dry blending. Volume ratio of TiB_2 and Al is 1:4.

Fig.4 Relationship between sintering temperature and sintering time of 20vol% TiB_2 /Al mixture mixed by wet blending and dry blending.

Relative density of TiB_2 /Al composites prepared by wet blending and dry blending was 97.0% and 99.8%, respectively. Composites have relatively high density compared with the composites fabricated by hot-pressing. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between sintering temperature and sintering time for wet blending and dry blending. The relation curves between sintering temperature and sintering time for wet blending and dry blending are very similar. After rapid heating till 500°C, the heating velocity was slow down till 530°C.

Fig. 5 Relationship between relative density and sintering time for spark sintering at 823K with 50MPa of applied pressure.

Fig. 5 is the relationship between sintering time and density of monolithic Al block and TiB_2 /Al composites obtained from wet blending and dry blending. Usually, spark sintering process was divided into three stages. 1st stage shows slow densification speed. In this stage, necking between particles was formed by the break of oxide film on particle, which is caused by the local heat-generation in arc discharge and the elevating temperature during pulse electric current in early stage. 2nd stage shows the heavy increment of relative density by the compressive plastic deformation. 3rd stage shows the slow densification. In this stage, pores introduced by sintering shrank and vanished by high temperature creep deformation. In this study, 2nd stage starts around over 500 °C, heavy densification was observed, and 3rd stage start at 530 °C. But obvious densification was not observed during keeping stage

for 1.8ks as shown in figs. 2, 4 and 5. In fig. 5, 1st stage was not observed in sintering for monolithic Al powder and mixture powder. The densification speed during 2nd stage in sintering was monolithic Al powder, wet blended powder and dry blended powder in early order.

Fig. 6 Schematic illustration showing the deformation and the transfer of the materials at the contact particles.

TiB₂ particles do not have plastic deformation and shows no sintering at this sintering temperature. It seems that the existence of the TiB₂ particle becomes the factor to reduce the densification speed. When TiB₂ powders are mixed with Al powders, the contact of particles was classified in three ways; i.e. Al particle-Al particle (a-a), Al particle-TiB₂ particle (a-t) and TiB₂ - TiB₂ (t-t). At first, each contact during sintering is considered as probability. Furthermore, the increment of the relative density, when TiB₂ particles added to Al particles, is assumed the burying process for cavity, which is caused by plastic deformation and rearrangement of particles. Fig. 6 shows the schematic illustration showing the deformation and the transfer of the materials at the contact particles during sintering process. In this case, the increase of relative density for mixture powders, (D-D₀), is expressed as the equation (1).

$$(D - D_0) = \gamma_{a-a}(D_{a-a} - D_0) + \gamma_{a-t}(D_{a-t} - D_0) + \gamma_{t-t}(D_{t-t} - D_0) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Hence, } \gamma_{a-a} + \gamma_{a-t} + \gamma_{t-t} = 1$$

γ_{a-a} , γ_{a-t} and γ_{t-t} are probability of a-a, a-t and t-t contacts in blended powders, respectively. And, (D_{a-a}-D₀), (D_{a-t}-D₀) and (D_{t-t}-D₀) is the increase in relative density in each contact parts.

γ_{a-a} , γ_{a-t} and γ_{t-t} is expressed following equations (2)

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{a-a} &= (1 - V_p) \\ \gamma_{a-t} &= 2V_p(1 - V_p) \\ \gamma_{t-t} &= V_p^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 7 shows the relationship between volume fraction of TiB₂ particles and contact probability of γ_{a-a} , γ_{a-t} and γ_{t-t} . Probability of t-t contact at 20vol% TiB₂ is 4%. As t-t contact is independent to sintering, the existence of t-t contact seems to delay the sintering velocity. 4% seems small value. In actual, the densification speed of monolithic Al powders is slightly faster than that of mixed powders, because of no TiB₂ particle in Al powder. On the other hand, the densification speed of mixed powders by wet blending was faster than that of dry blending. Contact probability of γ_{t-t} for dry blending is higher than that of wet blending because of aggregation of TiB₂ particles in mixed powders by wet blending.

Fig.7 Relationship between volume fraction of TiB₂ particles in mixed powders and particles probability.

Consequently, 20vol% TiB₂/Al composite with high density was obtained by spark sintering under low temperature (530°C), low pressure (50MPa) and short time (1.8ks). In contrast, in order to obtain 20vol% TiB₂/Al composites with 98% in relative density by hot-pressing, the conditions of 660°C in temperature, 100MPa in applied pressure, 2 hour in loading time are required [5]. Furthermore, usually there are many cavities around the aggregation of TiB₂ particles in TiB₂/Al composites fabricated by hot-pressing. However, the cavities were not observed in the composites fabricated by spark sintering, which is characteristic of spark sintering. During spark sintering, it seems that the oxides films on the surface of starting Al powder was destroyed by ark discharge and then contact area between Al and TiB₂ increased. As Al and TiB₂ have good wettability, it seems the densification of composites during spark sintering is promoted. Especially, the densification of composites around aggregation area of TiB₂ seems to be promoted. As local joule heat was generated at contact area of particles because of spark during sintering, we calculated the temperature at particle contact area.

It assumes that local joule heat generation in particle contact area is not spread by radiation and heat conduction. Then, we consider the deformed particle model with r in radius by applied pressure, P , and temperature, T as shown in fig.8.

Fig. 8 Schematic illustration of Al particles which play the role of a resistive element during the pulse current pressure sintering process.

Fig. 9 shows the relationship between momentary increasing temperature and radius r_0 of contact circuit between particles obtained by calculation. If radius (r_0) condition of contact area is very small, momentary increasing temperature at contact area between particles just after a pulse electricity start is over 5000K, which is over 933K of melting temperature of pure Al. Consequently, it seems that local heat generation and melting of Al particles was occurred at contact area between Al particles. S. K. Rhee [6] reported the contact angle between single crystalline TiB₂ and molten Al at 840°C is 55°. D. A. Weirauch [7] reported contact angle between TiB₂ and molten Al is 10-20° at 990°C, and almost 0° at over 1025°C. Usually, as under 90° of contact angle lead to the penetration behavior, molten Al infiltrate to clearance between TiB₂ particles automatically. Spark sintering is able to fabricate dense TiB₂/Al composites because of local heat generation, which is over molten temperature of Al, compared with hot-pressing.

Fig. 9 Relationship between the temperature one pulse of current and radius of contact area.

Fig. 10 shows the dispersion configuration of TiB₂ particle in composite obtained from the wet and dry blending processes. The TiB₂ particles in composite obtained from the wet blending seems to disperse uniformly in Al matrix, but the TiB₂ particles in composite obtained from the dry blending tend to have aggregation. LN2D was estimated in order to evaluate the dispersibility of the TiB₂ particle quantitatively from photograph in Fig.10.

Fig. 10 SEM images of 20vol%TiB₂/Al composite by spark sintering process. The blending method of powders are (a) wet process and (b) dry process.

Fig.11 shows the variance of dispersibility (LN2D) of the TiB₂ particle in composites as a function of volume fraction of TiB₂ particles. Black line in fig. shows ideal uniform random distribution. Variances of LN2DR obtained from TiB₂/Al composites obtained from wet and dry blending were 8.05 and 13.88. Degree of the aggregation becomes higher so as to deviate from the curve obtained from ideal uniform random distribution. This result shows that the TiB₂ particles in composite obtained from the wet blending distributed more uniformly than that of dry blending. This is because the aggregation of TiB₂ particle remained after the dry mixture process.

Fig. 11 Variance of LN2DR obtained from TiB₂/Al composites mixed by Wet blending and Dry blending. Line shows the variance of LN2DR obtained from uniform random structure of TiB₂/Al composites as a function of volume fraction of TiB₂ particles.

Fig. 12 Electrical conductivity of pure Al block, TiB₂ block and 20vol%TiB₂/Al composite.

Fig. 12 is an electric conductivity of the composite obtained from a pure Al block, TiB₂ block, the composites obtained from wet blending and dry blending. Pure Al block was fabricated by spark sintering under the same condition of composite preparation. The electric conductivity of pure aluminum block and the TiB₂ block was $38 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$ and $12 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$, respectively. On the other hand, the electric conductivity of the composite from wet blending and dry blending was $22 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$ and $27 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$, respectively. The electric conductivity of the composite from dry blending was higher than that of wet blending. Theoretical value

was estimated by Chang's model [8], which is applied to particle dispersed metal matrix composites. This model is expressed following equations;

$$\rho_c = \rho_1 \eta + \rho_m (1 - \eta) \quad (3)$$

$$= \rho_m \left\{ 1 - \eta + \frac{4\rho_m \rho_p}{\eta \sqrt{[4\rho_p - (\rho_p - \rho_m)\pi\eta^2][\rho_p - \rho_m]\pi}} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{(\rho_p - \rho_m)\pi\eta^2}{\sqrt{4\rho_p - (\rho_p - \rho_m)\pi\eta^2}} \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

Hence, ρ is electrical resistivity, and η is volume fraction. This model needs the following assumption; 1) There is no reaction phase between particle and matrix. 2) Particles disperse uniformly in matrix. 3) Electron moves easily without resistance between particle and electron. It is well known there is no reaction between Al and TiB₂. As Al and TiB₂ is electrical conducting material, the electrical conductivity at the interface between Al and TiB₂ seems to be very high. Therefore this model is suitable for predicting the electrical conductivity of this composite. The theoretical value of electrical conductivity is $32.0 \times 10^4 \Omega^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$, which is higher than the experimental results. It is considered low electrical conductivity is caused by the effect of the dispersibility. But the very low electrical conductivity of the electrical conductivity of the experimental result and the big difference of electrical conductivity between the composites obtained from wet process and dry process is inexplicable. It seems residual stress affect to the degradation of electrical conductivity. The residual stress occurs in a matrix in a cooling process of the composites preparation. The residual stress generates the lattice distortion, and degrades the electrical conductivity.

Adjustment of electrical conductivity was calculated under the viewpoint of the quantity of deformation region around the TiB₂ particles. If the difference of electrical conductivity between experimental result and theoretical value obtained from Chang's model, plastic deformation area in Al around TiB₂ particle is obtained by using following equations [9, 10].

$$(\alpha - 1) \propto \frac{B\varepsilon}{bd} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_c'(p) = \sigma_c(p) \left[1 - \left(\frac{\alpha^3 - 1}{\alpha^2} \right) V_p \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Hence, σ is electrical conductivity, α is plastic deformation region, V_p is volume fraction of dispersion particles, B is constant, ε is $\Delta \text{CTE} \times \Delta T$, d is average diameter of particles, and b is Burger's vector of Al matrix. Table 2 shows the calculation result of deformation region α of Al matrix in TiB₂/Al composite. Thermal expansion of Al and TiB₂ are $23.1 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$ and $3.7 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, respectively, and the difference of the thermal expansion between Al and TiB₂ becomes $19.3 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$. Deformation region α of TiB₂/Al composites obtained from dry process was larger than that of wet process. Therefore plastic deformation in the matrix by the difference of thermal expansion in the composites obtained from wet blending is bigger than that of wet blending because of the uniform distribution of TiB₂ particles in matrix. It seems the increment of strain caused by plastic deformation zone reduce the electrical conductivity of the composites.

Table 2 Experimental and theoretical α values for 20vol%TiB₂/Al composites.

TiB ₂ /Al	d [μm]	B	ΔCTE [10 ⁻⁶ /K]	ΔT [K]	E [10 ⁻²]	α [exp]
Wet blending	2.62	12	19.4	537	1.04	2.81
Dry blending						1.47

Then, the area ratio of matrix, particles and deformation region in matrix was estimated as shown in Fig. 13, which is calculated by using the results in table 2. The area ratio of the composites was defined as 1 or 100%. Area ratio of the deformation region in composites obtained from wet blending and dry blending are 136% and 23%. It seems that the all matrix in the composites obtained from wet blending was damaged by plastic deformation because over 100%. On the other hand, deformation region of the composites obtained from dry blending was 23%, and the matrix area without deformation is 57%. Hence, it is considered the composites obtained from dry blending was degraded the damage area by agglutinating TiB₂

particles, and consequently, the electrical conductivity of the composites obtained from dry blending is higher than that of wet blending. But, as the deformation region of the composites obtained from wet blending is over 100%, we have to consider the degree of deformation, if we consider the degradation of electrical conductivity of the composites obtained from wet process, quantitatively.

Fig. 13 Area fraction of Al, TiB₂ and deformation area of 20v.%TiB₂/Al composites.

4. Conclusion

20vol%TiB₂/Al composites with high density over 97% were obtained by using spark sintering process. The TiB₂/Al composites have relatively good electrical conductivity. But, the distribution of TiB₂ particles in composites affect to the electrical conductivity. Uniform distribution of TiB₂ particle led to degrade the electrical conductivity because of the increment of strain field.

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